

H2020 - Research and Innovation Action

APPLICATE

Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: Modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE

Grant Agreement No: 727862

Deliverable No. 7.1
Website including online tool
for end-user feedback

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report concerns Deliverable D7.1 Website including online tool for end-user feedback. The report provides a short description of the official project website and its main parts. In Annex N°1 one can find the current web tree and screen-shots of pages of the website.

The APPLICATE website is the project's main gateway to external stakeholders and serves to disseminate the latest information about the project, its implementation progress.

The website will be regularly updated and further developed as needed during the lifetime of the project. News about the project, the latest project results, and information about interesting events and activities related to the project will be regularly updated. The site will also feature information about research concerning APPLICATE's core area of focus, such as the Arctic's connections to weather and climate in mid-latitudes.

Special emphasis will be placed on cooperation and linkages to other projects and activities of importance and relevance to promote synergies and increase exposure, including the EU-funded projects Intaros, Blue Action and EuPolarNet, as well as the WMO YOPP project.

The project will also be actively promoted through social media channels (Facebook and Twitter), linking to the project website whenever relevant.

Project partners are able to access and share documents, information, data and communicate internally via the website's restricted-access intranet.

The project website went live to the general public on January 2nd, 2017.

The website can be found at: www.applycate.eu

INTRODUCTION

Background and objectives

The APPLICATE project aims to investigate ways to improve weather and climate prediction in the face of a rapidly changing Arctic. As part of the communication and dissemination activities within the project, members of the consortium have set up a user-friendly website to act as the main information portal for the project and the project's main gateway to various stakeholders.

Designed and hosted by the Arctic Portal, with the input and feedback of other beneficiaries, the website will be a central information hub for the APPLICATE project, featuring detailed information about the project. The website will evolve and grow over time as more events and deliverables from the project become available and the needs of the project change over time.

Organisation of this report

First, the general outline of the website design will be presented. Next, the content and each section of the website will be described. Then, the website dissemination strategy and the plan of the website updates will be presented. At the end, there is an Annex section with the website tree and screen-shots of pages of the website.

PROJECT WEBSITE

General information about the website design

The home page of the website features a banner with the APPLICATE logo at the top of the website along with a menu bar across the top providing links to the different sections of the website (Home, About the project, News, Reports, Animations, Contact us, Intranet). Each section will be described in further below.

Just below the main menu bar of the website is a slider banner on which key announcements about the project can be made. The slider banner can be changed and updated as necessary. At the moment, the slider banners feature two slides that introduce the project's objectives, a map showing the beneficiary countries and the partner logos with links to the section of the website where all APPLICATE beneficiaries are listed.

A link to the Intranet (for use only by beneficiaries and invited participants to upload documents and take part in forum discussions and is an integral part of the website's "end-user feedback" mechanisms) is also featured on the home page of the website.

On the left-hand side of the website, is a panel where the three latest news items are displayed. The bottom left-hand corner of the home page features buttons linking to the social media accounts (Facebook and Twitter) that have been created to promote the APPLICATE project.

As of the writing of this report, new buttons are being placed on the home page of the home page of the website providing key information about the project. More information about what is intended for these sections is described below. The purpose of these buttons will be to highlight the most important information and aspects about the APPLICATE project and to make it visually obvious for first-time visitors to the website.

The required acknowledgement that the APPLICATE project has received funding under the EU's Horizon 2020 Programme accompanied by the EU flag is clearly mentioned at the bottom of each page of the website.

It is also important to point out that, as mentioned in the description of the objectives of Work Package 7 in Annex 1 (Part A) of the Grant Agreement, the APPLICATE website will evolve and change over the course of the project to reflect the project's changing needs.

As stated under Task 7.1.2 - On-line communication and tools:

"A website will be designed to contain and offer the project description and its various outputs like public reports, general information, and news and dissemination material. The website will be initially set up to identify the project (providing visual identity materials and templates in a password protected partners area) and promote early engagement with other EU projects, international initiatives and communities (D7.1). In a second phase, the structure and contents will be critically revised, taking into account all the feedback collected from both partners and stakeholders, and modified accordingly (MS 7.5) so that it can take a role in serving more specific needs: promoting project results with high impact multimedia communication material, disseminating promotional campaigns of the project through social media (Facebook and Twitter accounts), publishing press releases and providing online feedback mechanisms to the target audiences, including the users and stakeholders contacted in Task 7.2. The website will include a compilation of skill training resources relevant for early career researchers in the APPLICATE project."

This report will serve to describe the APPLICATE website at the time of the writing of the report. Further amendments can be made as the website evolves over the course of the APPLICATE project's lifetime.

It should also be noted that the skill training resources section of the website stipulated in the description of Task 7.1.2 will be added after these resources have been created.

Content

The APPLICATE website URL is: www.applycate.eu. The website tree is presented in Annex N° 1, and screen-shots of pages of the website are presented in Annex N° 2.

2.2.1. The website currently features seven main sections accessible via the main menu bar across the home page of the website as well as latest news section on the home page:

i. HOME:

The home page features a banner with the APPLICATE logo at the top of the website along with a menu bar across the website providing links to the different sections of the website. It features links to six different items:

- Home
- About the project
- News
- Reports
- Animations
- Contact us
- Intranet

By clicking “Home” at any place on the website, the user is automatically re-directed back to the home page of the website.

ii. ABOUT THE PROJECT:

Visitors to this section of the website will learn more about the APPLICATE project, its objectives, key questions and expected outcomes from the work of the beneficiaries during the project. This section also features information about all beneficiaries involved in the APPLICATE project and has links to all beneficiaries' websites. The last section of this part of the website features descriptions of each Work Package – their objectives, leading structures, partners participating in each Work Package, and contact information for those leading each work package.

iii. NEWS:

This section of the website gives the latest news about the APPLICATE project and also news about research, activities, and events related to the themes of project such as Arctic climate and weather,

climate and weather prediction, and linkages between the Arctic and mid-latitudes in the Northern Hemisphere.

iv. REPORTS:

This section will serve as a place to post all reports to be made available publicly related to the APPLICATE project, as well as press releases.

v. ANIMATIONS:

This section contains a collection of animations created by beneficiaries involved in the consortium that illustrate different changes in Arctic region, such as Arctic sea ice thickness changes. As researchers from beneficiary organisations involved in the project work primarily with climate and weather modelling, this section allows them to highlight some of the visualisations of their modelling activities, wherever possible.

vi. CONTACT US:

This section provides the contact details for representatives of the APPLICATE project that members of the media can contact in case of press inquiries.

vii. INTRANET:

This section features a login page that allows users of the APPLICATE Intranet (which includes members of beneficiary organisation within the APPLICATE consortium and invited guests) to have access to a password-protected common collaboration platform. Users can upload draft versions of documents and take part in topical discussion forums related to the work of the project. This is one existing channel that can be considered an “online feedback mechanism”

The Intranet also serves as an archive for the project. All documents related to the project (Grant Agreement, etc.) as well as presentations from APPLICATE meetings will be uploaded to a special “archive” section of the Intranet.

2.2.2. The website also features six quick-reference buttons accessible via the home page:

The purpose of these buttons will be to highlight the most important information and aspects about the APPLICATE project and to make it visually obvious where to find relevant information for first-time visitors to the website. These buttons are also more obvious on mobile devices. It should be noted that these sections are currently under development and subject to change.

i TASK:

This section will provide a quick link to section of the website describing the APPLICATE project's main tasks and objectives

ii. STAKEHOLDERS

This section will provide a quick link to the section of the website describing the main stakeholders of the APPLICATE project

iii. TRAINING

This section will provide a quick link to the section of the website that will contain information about the training activities such as webinar series, summer school, online course, and other training options for early career scientists

iv. CONSORTIUM

This section will give a quick link to the part of the website describing each member of the APPLICATE project consortium

v. OUTREACH

This section will have information on the outreach activities carried out within the project as well as outreach and communication materials.

vi. MEDIA

This section will provide a quick link to media materials such as press releases, a picture and multimedia library, project videos and animations produced by the consortium members

DISSEMINATION AND UPDATES

The website will be disseminated to the public via different channels: social media accounts on Twitter and Facebook; printed materials that are to be disseminated on the seminars, conferences, training sessions and workshops within and outside of the project; other media that feature the project in its materials.

This report describes the functionalities and the structure of the website prepared by 28 of February. The first version of the website went live on January 2nd, 2017. The website will be updated on a regular basis, and new materials will be added throughout the duration of the project. Moreover, other changes in the main menu, sub-pages of the website, and extra graphics may be added as needed, especially if and when users and stakeholder groups provide feedback about the website. The APPLICATE consortium sees the website as an evolving, dynamic tool designed to fit the needs of its users as users' needs evolve.

ANNEXES

Annex 1. Home page

LOGO/NAME						
HOME	ABOUT	NEWS	REPORTS	ANIM	CONTACT US	INTRANET
NEWS FACEBOOK TWITTER			GOALS			
			PARTNERS			
			QUESTIONS			
			OUTCOMES			
			WP			
			FORUM			

	BANNER		
	TASK	STAKEHOLDER	TRAINING
	CONSORTIU M	OUTREACH	MEDIA

About the project page

BANNER
About the project

News page

News 1
News 2
News 3

Reports

Document 1	Document 2
Document 3	Document 4

Animations

Banner
Text
Links to gif
Videos

Annex 2. Screenshots of the website

Home page

APPLICATE
www.applycate.eu
Advanced prediction in Polar regions and beyond

HOME ABOUT THE PROJECT NEWS REPORTS ANIMATIONS CONTACT US INTRANET

Latest News

Registration for ECRA General Assembly 2017 Extended to 28 February
The 2017 European Climate Research Alliance (ECRA) general assembly will take place on 7 and 8 March in Brussels. The deadline for registration has been extended to 28 February.
23 Feb 2017

APPLICATE Kickoff Meeting Gets Underway in Bremerhaven
Over the next two days (8-9 February) representatives from the 16 partner organisations taking part in the EU Horizon 2020-funded APPLICATE project will be meeting at Klimahaus (Climate House) in Bremerhaven, Germany, to begin their collaborative efforts to improve climate and weather prediction for the Arctic and the mid-latitudes of the Northern Hemisphere, as well as contributing to improved Arctic observations.
8 Feb 2017

EU Horizon 2020 Project Studying Arctic's Connections to Weather and Climate in Europe, Asia and North America Kicks Off Bremerhaven, 14 November 2016
An EU-financed project investigating ways to improve weather and climate prediction in the face of a rapidly changing Arctic officially started this month.
3 Jan 2017

RSS People Facebook Twitter

APPLICATE
EU Horizon 2020 Project Studying Arctic's Connections to Weather and Climate in Europe, Asia and North America

TASK

STAKEHOLDERS

TRAINING

CONSORTIUM

OUTREACH

MEDIA

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APPLICATE (Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE), an €8 million project financed by the EU HORIZON 2020 Research and Innovation programme, involves 16 partners from nine countries (Belgium, France, Germany, Iceland, Norway, Russia, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom) and will be carried out over a period of four years.

The multinational and multidisciplinary consortium will work to enhance weather and climate prediction capabilities not only in the Arctic, but also in Europe, Asia, and North America.

A focus on the Arctic is important for improved predictions of weather and climate in the mid-latitudes because the changes taking place in the Arctic due to climate change—the retreat of sea ice, warming seas and a warming atmosphere—have the potential to influence weather and climate in the mid-latitudes. According to several studies (the most recent of which was published in Nature Climate Change in October 2016), a warming Arctic can, in fact, lead to prolonged periods of severe weather and cold spells in the mid-latitudes.

The impacts of severe weather on commerce and infrastructure can be significant, so having adequate tools to predict when and how severe weather systems will affect Europe, Asia and North America is vital to inhabitants of these regions. The APPLICATE project is bringing together an international team of experts in weather and climate prediction to improve climate and weather forecasting models to work on improving prediction tools while expanding and improving observational capabilities in the Arctic.

[APPLICATE Grant Agreement](#)

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[▶ Read more ...](#)

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[▶ Read more ...](#)

EU Horizon 2020 Project Studying Arctic's Connections to Weather and Climate in Europe, Asia and North America Kicks Off

Bremerhaven, 14 November 2016

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[ANIMATIONS](#)
[CONTACT US](#)
[INTRANET](#)

Home > Root > Open Documents

Open Documents

Documents that are open to the general public

Default Asc 10

Applycate Kick off meeting

Tuesday, 07 February 2017 Super User Open Documents

8-9 February 2017 Klimahaus Bremerhaven Am Längengrad 8, 27568 Bremerhaven, Germany

Download

Version 1.0 Hits 46 Downloads 19 Rating ★★★★★ Comments 0

Launch Press Release

Thursday, 05 January 2017 Super User Open Documents

Applycate launch press release 14th November 2016

Download

Version 1.0 Hits 35 Downloads 4 Rating ★★★★★ Comments 0

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Home > Animations

Animations

Models are valuable tools because they allow one to reconstruct several variables that are not necessarily easy to observe. The following are some animations created by consortium members that illustrate this point.

- Arctic sea ice thickness from a 1/4° global simulation with the ocean-sea ice model NEMO-LIM3 over the year 1983
- Arctic sea ice concentration from a 1/4° global simulation with the ocean-sea ice model NEMO-LIM3 over the year 1983
- Effect of horizontal resolution on sea ice concentration as simulated by the ocean-sea ice model NEMO-LIM3 over the year 1984

Videos

FESOM frontier simulation. Arctic sea ice.

Advanced prediction in Polar regions and beyond

HOME ABOUT THE PROJECT NEWS REPORTS ANIMATIONS CONTACT US INTRANET

Home > Contact us

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Advanced prediction in Polar regions and beyond

HOME ABOUT THE PROJECT NEWS REPORTS ANIMATIONS CONTACT US INTRANET

Home > Intranet

This is the login page for users of the APPLICATE Intranet. Members of the APPLICATE consortium and invited guests can upload consortium documents and take part in topical discussion forums related to the work of the project. If you do not have a user name and password for the APPLICATE Intranet and would like to request access, please contact Evar Karl Karlsson at Arctic Portal at: aevar@arcticportal.org .

Username *

Password *

Remember me

[Forgot your password?](#)

[Forgot your username?](#)

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